

Data-based evaluation of isospin-breaking to tau two-pion spectral functions for muon $g - 2$ prediction

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Abstract

Tau data, especially the two-pion spectral function, can be used to compute the hadronic vacuum polarization (HVP) contribution to the standard model muon $g - 2$ prediction after correcting for isospin violations between tau and e^+e^- . These corrections are usually computed theoretically with uncertainties sometimes difficult to establish. We present here a data-based evaluation of the most critical correction to the charged-current pion form factor available in tau decays. The result leads to a very competitive estimate of the HVP contribution.

1 Introduction

The muon $g - 2$ (a_μ) has been a subject of active research since a long date. It can be precisely measured and predicted. The final measurement of the Fermilab muon $g - 2$ experiment has reached a precision of 127 ppb [1]. The predictions [2] used to show a discrepancy of more than three standard deviations with the measurements. The predictions have the largest uncertainty from the contributions of hadronic vacuum polarization (HVP), which have been evaluated until recently with a data-driven method by using the electron-positron annihilation data to hadrons in the dispersion relations. The discrepancy could have been a first sign of new physics. Unfortunately, with the recent measurement of the dominant two-pion channel from CMD3 [3], the discrepancy among different two-pion measurements becomes so large that a new data-driven prediction using the combined e^+e^- data becomes impossible. For this reason, the lattice-based calculation was used as the new prediction in version 2025 of the white paper of the muon $g - 2$ theory initiative (WP2025), though its precision is still quite limited [4]. An overview of the current status is shown in Figure 1.

It is important to have independent and precise measurements to clarify the situation. Tau data provide such an alternative. Isospin breaking (IB) corrections need, however, to be applied to the tau data. Some of the corrections are currently model dependent. In WP2025, the uncertainties of the model dependent corrections were inflated following recommendations from theorists [4]. This is an unsatisfactory solution.

In this talk, we present data-driven form-factor (FF) related IB corrections, based on results detailed in Ref. [5].

2 Data and results

The idea of using the tau spectral functions (SF) as inputs for the HVP prediction was originally proposed in Ref. [6]. For the dominant two-pion channel, four experiments ALEPH, Belle, CLEO

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Figure 1: An overview of dispersive data predictions to a_μ using e^+e^- and IB-corrected tau data as well as lattice based predictions expressed as differences to the direct Fermilab measurement. The inner error bar represents the total uncertainty from the two-pion contribution, the outer one the total uncertainty when adding in quadrature the other contributions to the full a_μ and the intermediate one for tau corresponds to the inflated IB correction uncertainty.

and OPAL have measured its SF under very different experimental conditions [7–10]. ALEPH provided the best normalization (namely the branching fraction) measurement while Belle had the best shape measurement. OPAL data had limited precision and it will not be used in the following analysis as no FF fit was performed in the original publication.

The IB corrections contain a leading short-distance electroweak (EW) correction S_{EW} which is energy independent, and several energy dependent corrections: a small long-distance radiation correction $G_{EM}(s)$, the final state radiation (FSR) correction, the neutral and charged pion mass difference-related phase space correction, and the neutral and charged rho mass and width difference-related corrections (Δm_ρ and $\Delta \Gamma_\rho$) in the relevant FFs. The largest uncertainty inflation proposed in Ref. [4] was on the last correction. Therefore, a data-driven evaluation of Δm_ρ and $\Delta \Gamma_\rho$ has been conducted in this analysis [5].

To determine the mass and width of the neutral and charged rho resonances, the Gounaris-Sakurai (GS) FF parameterization [11] is used to fit individual two-pion data from BABAR [12], BES [13], CMD2 [14–17], CMD3 [3], SND [18], SND20 [19] and KLOE [20–22] for e^+e^- and ALEPH, Belle and CLEO for tau.

The BABAR measurement covers the largest energy range from threshold to 3 GeV. In total, 19 free parameters are used to fit the whole energy spectrum: one normalization parameter, 6 parameters (m_ρ , Γ_ρ , m_ω , Γ_ρ , $|c_\omega|$ and ϕ_ω) to describe the dominant ρ -resonance component at low energy and its interference with the ω -resonance, 12 other parameters to model the three high-mass resonances ρ' , ρ'' and ρ''' and their interferences. The other data are mostly limited to the low energy regions. A common upper limit of 0.9 GeV is used to fit all these data using nevertheless the same parameterization as for BABAR, except that the parameters for the high-mass resonances are fixed to those from the BABAR fit for all the datasets and no ω -resonance related parameters are needed for τ . The normalization parameter is introduced to decouple the observed discrepancy among the different datasets from the parameters of interest, m_ρ and Γ_ρ , which control the shape of the spectrum.

In all the cases, the data can be well fitted with the GS parameterization. Three examples are shown in Figure 2. The corresponding χ^2 values per number of degrees of freedom are 0.99, 0.92 and 1.8, respectively. The latter is somewhat large since some of the uncertainties were

Figure 2: Examples of three selected fits for BABAR, CMD3 and Belle.

Figure 3: Left: Comparison for all e^+e^- experiments of their $a_\mu^{\text{HVP,LO}}$ integral in the common mass range 0.600–0.883 GeV (left column), the fitted normalization factor (middle column) and their ratio (right column). Middle: A compilation of the fitted ρ mass values from e^+e^- data in the top panel in comparison with those from τ data (bottom panel). Right: Same style as for the middle plot but showing the fitted Γ_ρ values.

not included in the covariance matrix used for the fit. These uncertainties are, however, added to the total uncertainty as done in the original publication [8].

The fitted normalization, m_ρ and Γ_ρ are shown in Figure 3. It is interesting to observe that the normalization of some of the data deviates significantly from one but it is strongly correlated with the calculated leading order (LO) HVP contribution to a_μ . Among the fitted m_ρ and Γ_ρ from different e^+e^- data, CMD3 is by far the most precise one. The tau data from all three datasets have limited precision. The corresponding weighted averages as indicated with the vertical error bands give $\Delta m_\rho = m_{\rho^0} - m_{\rho^\pm} = -0.30(38)$ MeV and $\Delta \Gamma_\rho = \Gamma_{\rho^0} - \Gamma_{\rho^\pm} = -0.58(1.01)$ MeV. The latter result can be compared with the recently improved model dependent calculation of $\Delta \Gamma_\rho = -0.62(22)$ from Ref. [23].

Several systematic checks have been performed. One is the dependence on the FF parameterization. As an alternative choice, the Kuhn-Santamaria (KS) parameterization [24] has also been used giving $\Delta m_\rho^{\text{KS}} = -0.91(48)$ MeV and $\Delta \Gamma_\rho^{\text{KS}} = -0.83(1.00)$ MeV. Allowing the complex amplitudes for the ρ' and ρ'' resonances be free in the fits to the tau data, instead of using the fitted parameters for high-resonances from BABAR, a difference of +0.38 MeV and -0.25 MeV has been observed for the mass and width, respectively. The model dependence of G_{EM} is checked to be below 0.1 MeV for both m_ρ and Γ_ρ .

Table 1: Different contributions for IB corrections $\Delta a_\mu^{\text{HVP,LO}}$ applied to the τ result (in units of 10^{-10}). For each entry, statistical and systematic uncertainties are combined and given in the first bracket, while the second bracket in the last three entries indicates the uncertainty from the form factor parametrization.

Source of IB	$\Delta a_\mu^{\text{HVP,LO}} (10^{-10})$
S_{EW}	-12.21(15)
G_{EM}	-1.87(96)
FSR	+4.65(44)
β^3 cross-section	-7.69
$\rho - \omega$ interference	+3.22(9)(8)
Form factor Δm_ρ	+0.06(10)(2)
Form factor $\Delta \Gamma_\rho$	+1.62(2.92)(1.39)
Sum	-12.22(3.41)

The resulting IB corrections of this study on $a_\mu^{\text{HVP,LO}}$ are shown as items “Form factor Δm_ρ ” and “Form factor $\Delta \Gamma_\rho$ ” together with the other IB corrections in Table 1. Our total uncertainty of 3.2 is to be compared with the inflated one of 4.7 in Ref. [4]. The item “ $\rho - \omega$ interference” is also updated with respect to Refs. [25, 26] as a by-product of the e^+e^- fits in this analysis.

3 Summary

Data-based FF related IB corrections have been derived [5] using the GS and KS parameterizations, resulting in $\Delta a_\mu^{\text{HVP,LO}}(\Delta m_\rho) = +0.06(10)(2) \times 10^{-10}$ and $\Delta a_\mu^{\text{HVP,LO}}(\Delta \Gamma_\rho) = +1.62(2.92)(1.39) \times 10^{-10}$, where the first uncertainty is due mainly to the limited tau data precision in the GS fits and the second the difference between the GS and KS fits. Therefore, the dominant IB correction related to the FF is from the width difference between the charged and neutral rho resonances. The uncertainties, despite limited precision of the tau data, are competitive with the inflated one quoted in WP2025 [4]. Improved tau data are needed to reduce the uncertainties. Our data-driven results are in excellent agreement with the improved model-dependent evaluation [23].

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